

EOSC Symposium 2024 reflections

Notes by Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (Version: Draft with introduction)

One of the biggest headlines from EOSC Symposium 2024 was definitely the launch of the [EOSC EU Node](#) with updates on the [build-up phase of the broader EOSC federation](#). The opening and closing sessions emphasised that EOSC has the full support of the European Commission, that there is a strong momentum and body of finished work to build on, and that now is the time to focus on science-driven showcases with tangible benefits. There were a lot of interesting sessions and while you can find the [recordings, slides and summaries on the website](#), I would like to invite those of you who can highlight something more specific to share your perspective.

About this document

Personal reflections from [EOSC Symposium 2024](#) summarised with a focus on [EOSC Opportunity Area Expert Group 2 \(OA2\): Metadata, Ontologies and Interoperability](#) activities and shared with the aim to support continued discussions and collaborative reporting.

Day 1 - 21 Oct

Opening: Some useful statements to reference on the direction of and commitment to EOSC. Knowledge as the 5th dimension to the European free market. Status update on EOSC EU Node launch and tripartite activities pre- and post-2027, as well as handbook consultations etc

INFRAEOSC projects session: Useful introduction to the OAs in general as well as main goals and contributions, reference to website updates, date and location for EOSC Winter School 2025 (Seville, Spain 20–23 Jan), panel received questions reflecting needs for authoritative source for implementation requirements, possibility to promote project outputs to authoritative guidance, and the interoperability board concept was raised.

Unconference on restricted access: Introduction to the EOSC-ENTRUST, TITAN & SIESTA projects that all address restricted data processing environments, followed by a panel responding to questions highlighting synergies, importance of agreeing on solutions to support semantic interoperability as well as reflections on translating (legal) risk to implementation requirements

Day 2 - 22 Oct

EOSC Federation: EU Node launched and a number of other prospective thematic/national nodes (50+) to work with. Aiming to establish federation-wide policies and capabilities to demonstrate end-to-end use cases next year. EOSC EU Node now available through eduGAIN/EU login. Work with end users, nodes and wider engagement to inform and test interoperability.

Scholarly data: Interoperability framework for SKGs developing with input through RDA, repository networks and EU projects. A core framework with mechanisms for domain extensions or extensions for services that can be considered for inclusions in future versions. Could connect DMPs, digital objects etc and

built on relations from established vocabularies (currently specified in a JSON-LD context).

Federation handbook: Work in progress based on in-kind contributions to create the first version of a document that describes how the EOSC federation works. The document will change over time as the federation evolves. Serving as a guide for service providers and prospective EOSC nodes. Open call for comments, more comprehensive feedback / contributions also accepted. Challenging balance between being concise and precise.

EOSC Interoperability: Panel covering technical and semantic interoperability introduced with examples including I-ADOPT, FAIR Digital Objects and Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework served as great examples of different aspects of the solutions. Concluding statement by Carole on the lines of the path to interoperability being a mix of evolution and revolution.

Day 3 - 23 Oct

FAIR Data and AI: There is an overlap in the desirable characteristics of data used for AI applications and FAIR data and in this context the FAIR acronym could also be read as Findable and AI Ready. Retroactive and ad-hoc data curation is both challenging and costly, and metadata about the training data are required for the assessment of a model. Tracking and visualising impact and desirable metrics to the community can create incentives for FAIRification. AI can help in FAIRifying data, such as mapping free text variable descriptions to I-ADOPT using LLMs, the choice of model must be a weighted balance between cost of training/using the model and quality of results.

Thematic contributions: There are many examples of domain or data type specific RIs and other collaborations that strive to improve access to and data quality for its users, such as NFDI, BBMRI, CLARIN, Blue-Cloud, and ELIXIR. They provide data catalogues and discovery, software tools and environments, training and expert support, and other services based on needs in the projects and communities that use them. Candidate nodes are federations of federations, with national nodes federating more local or specialised nodes. EOSC EU Node can provide solutions if something is missing when planning on to set up a new node. Thematic nodes can drive development of use cases for integration of data and services in the EOSC EU Node and support communities in developing and adopting FAIRification practices.